

1 **A gene expression signature for bipolar disorder.**

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7 We applied transcriptomic methods to drug and target discovery in psychiatric diseases, using
8 RNA-sequencing to measure total transcription in the nucleus accumbens (nACC) in 8 healthy individuals
9 and 12 individuals with bipolar disorder. We observed activation of the *ASIC* family ion channel *ASIC4*. In
10 humans with bipolar disorder in the nACC, the alpha synuclein interacting protein *SYNCAIP* was
11 repressed. In bipolar disorder we observed activation of the receptor *Iglon5*, and the signaling component
12 *Adgrd1*. The voltage gated ion channel *Nkain1* was a target of interest in bipolar or manic depression, as
13 was the olfactory receptor *Or10a2*.

14 Citations

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